

**ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ФАНЛАР
АКАДЕМИЯСИ МИНТАҚАВИЙ БЎЛИМИ
ХОРАЗМ МАЪМУН АКАДЕМИЯСИ**

**ХОРАЗМ МАЪМУН
АКАДЕМИЯСИ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

Ахборотнома ОАК Раёсатининг 2016-йил 29-декабрдаги 223/4-сон қарори билан биология, қишлоқ хўжалиги, тарих, иқтисодиёт, филология ва архитектура фанлари бўйича докторлик диссертациялари асосий илмий натижаларини чоп этиш тавсия этилган илмий нашрлар рўйхатига киритилган

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МУНДАРИЖА
ИҚТИСОДИЁТ ФАНЛАРИ

Abdullaev A.J., Raimova D.D. Avtotransport sohasida faoliyat yurituvchi tadbirkorlik sub'ektlarida outsorsing va undan foydalanishning afzalliklari	5
Abdurahmonova S.E. O'zbekiston temir yo'llarining rivojlanish imkoniyatlari va taraqqiyoti	8
Alimova D.T. Investitsiyani moliyalashtirishda aholi mablag'lari va tijorat amaliyotidagi ishtiroki	10
Allonazarov O.N. Mehmonxona xizmatlari bozorini rivojlantirishda raqamli texnologiyalarni qo'llashning ustuvor yo'nalishlari	14
Axrorova N.U. Talaba va yoshlar sayohati turlari hamda uning xususiyatlari	18
Babajanov J.F. Mintaqada kambag'allikni qisqarishni omillari	22
Baytanov O'M. Oziq-ovqat korxonalarida mahsulot sifatini mohiyati va unga ta'sir etuvchi omillar	25
Donayev Sh.B. Don mahsulotlari korxonalarida ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini baholash usullari	29
Kurpayanidi K.I. Economic transformation through institutional reforms: analysing challenges and perspectives of enterprise management	32
Matyakubov U.R. Marketing tadqiqotlari tizimining metodologik asoslari	36
Mirzayev A.T. O'zbekistonda turizm sohasida tadbirkorlik faoliyatini rivojlantirish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish	40
Mirzayev S.A. Qurilish sanoati korxonalarida boshqaruv samaradorligini baholash omillari	46
Nishonboyev D.E. Tadbirkorlik faoliyatining tashqi iqtisodiy faoliyati ko'rsatkichlari tizimi takomillashtirish	50
Qurbonova O. Mintaqada sanoat siyosatini shakllantirish ustuvor yo'nalishlari	54
Raxmonov S. Mintaqalarda innovatsion faoliyatini jadallashtirish ustuvor yo'nalishlari	57
Ruzimatov Sh.Kh. Chakana savdo korxonalarida brend nufuzini oshirishda inson resurslarini boshqarishning ahamiyati	60
Sattarov N.A. Innovatsion iqtisodiyot sharoitida qurilish korxonalar raqobatbardoshligining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	66
Sattarov N.A. Qurilish korxonalar raqobatbardoshligini oshirishning yo'nalishlari	69
Shakirova N.A. Tadbirkorlik sub'ektlarida aholi bandligini ta'minlashni muammolari va yechimlari	73
Xamroyeva M.B. Turizm sohasida xizmat ko'rsatish nosozliklari va ularni samarali bartaraf etish yo'llari	79
Абдугурапова Д.Ф. Ўзбекистонда суғурта муносабатлари ва ривожлантириш истикболлари	83
Атажонов Ж.О. Аграр соҳада кичик бизнес субъектлари кооперация алоқалари (КБСКА) ни ривожлантиришнинг ижтимоий-иқтисодий аҳамияти	88
Ахмедов М.Ш. Персонал мотивациясининг япония тажрибаси таҳлили	93
Ембергенова А. Қорақолпоғистон Республикаси давлат музейларининг туризм соҳасидаги роли ва уларни бошқариш аҳамияти	97
Жумабаева Д.Т. Агротуризм фаолиятининг таснифланиши ва ташкил этиш хусусиятлари	103
Жўраева З.Т. Инсон капитали самардорлигини баҳолашда хориж тажрибасини қўллашнинг концептуал асослари	108
Калимулина Н.В. Хорижий мамлакатларда қурилиш соҳасида кичик бизнесни давлат томонидан қўллаб-қувватлашнинг айрим илғор тажрибалари	113
Қуйжанов Х.А. Саноат корхоналарида иқтисодий салоҳият тушунчасининг моҳияти ва ижтимоий-иқтисодий аҳамияти	121

Мадрахимов Қ., Маткаримова И.А. Миллий ҳисоблар тизимини ишлаб чиқариш фаолияти билан боғлиқ асосий счёти ва уларни иқтисодий - статистик таҳлили	124
Махсудов Ш.С. Тўқимачилик саноатида инвестицион фаолиятни ривожлантириш орқали экспорт салоҳиятини ошириш тенденциялари	130
Мухитдинов Ш.Х., Саломов Ф. Минтақа туризмда хизмат кўрсатиш корхоналарининг гуруҳлаш ва уларни иқтисодий самарадорлик кўрсаткичларини таҳлил қилиш усуллари	132
Оллоқулова Ф.М. Маҳаллий бюджетлар даромадлар манбаини кенгайтириш йўналишлари	137
Саидов Д.Р. Ўзбекистон Республикасида автомобиль бизнесида сервис хизматларини ривожлантиришнинг ташкилий-иқтисодий механизмларини такомиллаштириш йўналишлари ва уларни амалга ошириш алгоритми	139
Сарыбаева А.Б. Хорижий инвестицияларни жалб этишда қулай инвестицион муҳитдан самарали фойдаланиш истиқболлари	147
Саттаров Ғ.А. Минтақа экспорт салоҳиятини оширишнинг ўзига хос жиҳатлари	153
Сатторкулов О.Т., Раҳматов К.У., Самадқулов М.И. Инновацион фаолиятини давлат томонидан қўллаб-қувватлаш ва ривожлантириш йўналишлари	156
Хабибулло Ҳожи М.А. Хоразм вилояти туризм салоҳияти хусусиятлари	163
Хабибулло Ҳожи М.А. Хоразм вилоятида туризмнинг ривожлантириш стратегик йўналишлари	166
Хамроқулов У.А. Озиқ-овқат саноати корхоналар инновацион салоҳиятини бошқаришнинг ўзига хос хусусиятлари	170

АРХИТЕКТУРА ФАНЛАРИ

Masharipova S.A., Xamidova B.A., G'oymatov O'.M. Savdo, umumiy ovqatlanish va maishiy xizmat ko'rsatish binolari	174
Qodirova S.A., Inogomov B.I., Raximov L.Sh. Madaniy va ma'rifiy markazlarining paydo bo'lish omillari va rivojlanish bosqichlari	177
Абдуҷаббарова М.Т. Проектирование основного производства на современных швейных предприятиях	180
Адилова М.С. Предпосылки использования водного фасада для стабилизации экологического состояния городов Узбекистана	183
Иногамов Б.И., Абдуҷаббарова М.Т., Алимджанов Р.И. Ўзбекистонда ганч ўймакорлиги санъатининг ривожланиши	189

Fikrimizcha, yuqorida keltirilgan texnologik yondashuv don mahsulotlari korxonalaridagi umumiy ishlab chiqarish sur'atlarini faqat bir omil yordamida aniqlanayotganligi tufayli korxonaning iqtisodiy salohiyati va ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini aks ettirishda to'liq tasavvurni bermaydi. Shu sababli jarayonga ta'sir etuvchi omillarning tizimli tahlilini amalga oshirishga maqsadga muvofiq deb hisoblaymiz.

Lekin Volkova E.A. natural dondan yem donini ishlab chiqarishdagi almashinuv energiyasining o'ltov birligiga asoslangan yem donini ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini iqtisodiy baholash usulini taklif qiladi va shu bilan birga don mahsulotlari samaradorligini aniqlashda donning ozuqaviylik/yem-xashaklik darajasini hisobga olish zarurligi g'oyasini ifodalaydi[8].

$$T_{AE_n} = \frac{X}{H * AE_n} \quad (1)$$

Bu yerda,

T_{AE_n} – natural donning almashinuv energiyasi birligining tannarxi, so'm

X – yem-xashak donini yetishtirish, yig'ishtirish va undan keyingi qayta ishlash xarajatlari (so'm/ga):

H- qayta ishlagandan keyingi donning hosildorligi, t/ga;

AE_n – qo'lga kiritilgan hosilning almashinuv energiyasi, MDj.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytish mumkinki, don qimmatli va almashtirib bo'lmaydigan bo'lib, aholining uglevod va oqsillarga bo'lgan ehtiyojining katta qismini qoplaydi. Biroq, u nafaqat non, balki chorva va parrandalar uchun ozuqa, shuning uchun ham sut, go'sht, tuxum va boshqa mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqarish manbai hisoblanadi. Konsentrlangan ozuqalar juda to'yimli. Ular ham mexanizatsiyalash va oziq-ovqat tayyorlash tizimlariga osongina mos keladi. Don yemini tayyorlash va tarqatish uchun sarflanadigan mehnat xarajatlari boshqa yemlarga qaraganda bir necha baravar kam. Zero, g'alla bozori xalq xo'jaligida yetakchi o'rinni egallaydi. Don strategik muhim mahsulot hisoblanadi.

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ECONOMIC TRANSFORMATION THROUGH INSTITUTIONAL REFORMS: ANALYSING CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES OF ENTERPRISE MANAGEMENT

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola iqtisodiy transformatsiya va korxonalarни boshqarish tizimlarida institutsional islohotlarни жорий этиши соҳасида тадқиқотлар ўтказиши билан боғлиқ моҳият, принциплар, усуллар ва муаммоларни аниқлашга бағишланган. У иqtisodiyёт ва менежментдаги ўзгаришлар билан боғлиқ жараёнларни чуқурроқ тушунишига

қаратилган бўлиб, ушбу шароитда корхоналарни ташкил этиши ва бошқаришида янги ёндашувларни ишлаб чиқиши учун асос яратади.

Kalit soʻzlar: таркибий ўзгаришлар, рақобатбардош компаниялар, менежментдаги инновациялар, компанияларни бошқариш тизимлари.

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена выявлению сущности, принципов, методов и проблем, связанных с проведением исследований в области трансформации экономики и внедрения институциональных реформ в системы управления предприятий. Она ставит своей целью более глубокое понимание процессов, связанных с изменениями в экономике и управлении, и предоставляет основы для разработки новых подходов к организации и управлению предприятиями в этих условиях.

Ключевые слова: структурные изменения, конкурентноспособные компании, инновации в управлении, управленческие системы компаний.

Abstract. This article is devoted to the identification of the essence, principles, methods and problems associated with research in the field of economic transformation and implementation of institutional reforms in the management systems of enterprises. It aims to better understand the processes associated with changes in the economy and management and provides a basis for the development of new approaches to the organisation and management of enterprises in these conditions.

Keywords: structural changes, competitive companies, innovations in management, management systems of companies.

Introduction. In today's environment of rapidly changing production and social structure, management is in a constant stage of development. In order for this development to be successful, it is essential to conduct research to find ways and opportunities for improvement and to identify alternative directions and innovations [2, 4, 5]. The level of development of enterprise management and the extensive knowledge and experience of management researchers and practitioners that have been accumulated in recent decades play an important role in the success of enterprises. Indeed, the success of enterprises depends on many factors and assessing the contribution and role of management to the overall success of an enterprise is a challenging task [3]. One of the key aspects of research on modern enterprises is to collect and analyse data reflecting the current situation and trends of the company nowadays. A clear picture of different areas of enterprise activities helps to identify the main directions for further development and making important management decisions.

Research Methods. The study used general scientific methods and techniques: scientific abstraction, grouping, qualitative expert assessments, quantitative assessments, comparative analysis and synthesis.

Results. According to recognised experts in the field of modern management such as Cheriet, F., Messeghem, K., Lagarde, V., McElwee, G., Brignall, S., & Ballantine, J., Joseph M. Juran, Womack, J. P., and others, the active improvement of the production processes of companies is becoming an integral part of modern management systems such as Quality Management System, Total Quality Management, Lean Manufacturing or Continuous Improvement. Undoubtedly, the successes achieved in this area are significant, but there is always room for further improvement for the industry. In accordance with the Presidential Decree No PP-4397 dated 18.07.2019 "On additional measures for accelerated development of the automotive industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan", additional steps are being taken to actively develop the automotive industry in the country. This decision will show an orientation towards further innovations and improvements in the industry, which can significantly contribute to its growth and improve the economic development of the country.

Within this document, the main objectives and indicators for the development of the automotive industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period from 2019 to 2023 have been defined: 1.

- Increasing the annual production volume of passenger cars up to 350 thousand units; 2.
- Increasing the level of localisation of passenger cars to an average of 60 per cent; 3. Expansion

of the annual production volume of trucks and buses up to 10 thousand units; 4. Increasing the volume of car exports to 100 thousand units annually; 5. Introduction of modern methods of corporate management and automated accounting system "ERP"; 6. Renewal of the car model range, including the production of a new modern model of passenger car available to the general public; 7. Attracting investors through initial public offering (IPO) of shares of at least two joint stock companies, which are part of Uzavtosanoat JSC, on domestic and international stock markets.

The goals and indicators defined in this document represent strategic objectives aimed at strengthening and developing the automotive industry in the country. Successful implementation of these activities contributes to the creation of a sustainable and prosperous automotive industry, promotes versatile economic growth and enhances competitiveness in the global arena.

The measures taken are aimed at boosting the development of the automotive industry in the country, as well as increasing its production capacity and technological modernisation. These steps contribute to the creation of modern and competitive cars that will be available to a wide range of consumers and have the potential to successfully occupy a sustainable position in the global market. These measures are an important driver of economic development and support the progressive transformation of the automotive industry. By stimulating innovation, developing new technologies and strengthening the competitiveness of enterprises, the country can ensure growth in the production of quality modern cars.

Discussions. In order to successfully achieve the set objectives, it is necessary to carry out a radical improvement in the organisation of enterprises' activities, with special attention to the improvement of the quality management system. This aspect plays a key role in the country's economy, and its successful improvement contributes to GDP growth, consumer satisfaction and inflation reduction.

Enterprises of Uzbekistan, such as JSC "Uzbekistan Havo Yollari", JSC "Navoiyazot", JSC "Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Combine", strive to use advanced management strategies and methods, including quality management systems. They demonstrate their commitment to progress by implementing the latest version of the international standard ISO 9001:2015. These large enterprises have successfully obtained certification of the following systems over the past three years: "Quality Management System" ISO 9001:2015, "Environmental Management System" ISO 14001:2015, "Occupational Health and Safety Management System" ISO 45001:2018 and "Energy Management System" ISO 50001:2018. These certifications confirm the enterprises' commitment to high standards of quality, environmental responsibility, concern for safety and efficient use of energy [1, 5]. They also reflect the enterprises' commitment to improving productivity, optimising processes and increasing the confidence of customers and partners. The implementation of these international standards proves the enterprises' readiness for continuous improvement and adoption of advanced management approaches. This makes them globally competitive and an important contribution to the country's sustainable economic growth.

As of 1 July 2023, the State Register of Certified Quality Management Systems (QMS) of the Republic of Uzbekistan has registered 10,582 enterprises and organisations that have successfully passed the certification procedure and confirmed compliance with international standards. These include: 10104 enterprises with ISO 9001 certification, 201 enterprises with ISO 14001 certification, 256 enterprises with OHSAS 18001 certification, 289 enterprises with ISO 22000 certification, 43 enterprises with ISO/TS 45 certification (quality assurance of supplied parts in the automotive industry) and 23 enterprises with GMP certification. The main attention of domestic enterprises in building quality management systems is paid to the International Standards ISO 9000. This indicates the wide spread and popularity of this standard among the business community in the country. ISO 9001 certification allows organisations to systematise their processes, improve their efficiency and ensure high quality of products or services, which helps to improve their competitiveness and the trust of customers and partners. In addition, there is also a significant number of enterprises that have obtained certification to other international standards such as ISO 14001, OHSAS 18001, ISO 22000, ISO/TS 45 and GMP. These standards reflect the enterprises' endeavour to comply with environmental, health, food safety and other important requirements, which is an indicator of their

responsibility and progressive approach to management. In general, the presence of a large number of certified enterprises testifies to the growing importance of quality management systems in the economy of Uzbekistan and the general orientation towards high standards and modern methods of management in business. This positive phenomenon contributes to the further development of the country's business environment and its successful integration into the global economy.

Organisation and stimulation of creative work of personnel in the sphere of product quality improvement and process optimisation is one of the main and most important tasks in the field of quality management and is an integral part of modern enterprise management.

Japanese companies demonstrated significant success in ensuring high quality of products due to the creative approach of their employees to work. For example, each employee of Japanese automotive companies on average offers 61.6 process improvements during the year, while their European counterparts have only 0.4 [7, 8].

In this regard, European and American researchers and practitioners in the field of quality management pay special attention to the study, adaptation and development of methods of employee involvement in the processes of product quality management and overall company development, as well as the formation of creative attitude of employees to their work. Research aimed at exploring the essence, methods and tools of quality management in Japanese enterprises has received considerable resources and has led to great successes. For example, the indicators of suggestions for improvements "KAIZEN" made 4.2 for the USA and 1.9 for European car plants [3, 6].

At the enterprises of JSC "Uzavtosanoat", especially at JSC "UzAuto Motors", JV LLC "Samarkand Automobile Plant" and JV LLC "UZ TRUCK AND BUS MOTORS", the involvement of employees in improving the quality of products and processes, as well as the development of their technical creativity, are of particular importance. This contributes to improving the efficiency, quality and competitiveness of enterprises, which ultimately affects their success in the market and the overall growth of the country's economy.

On the example of JSC "UzAuto Motors" it can be seen that since 2000, the company has deployed a system of suggestions for improving production, inspired by foreign partners and similar to rationalisation. During this time, there has been a noticeable increase in the activity of employees who bring suggestions for improvement. The rationalisation ideas implementation ratio (the ratio of implemented ideas to the total number of proposed ideas) has also increased significantly, indicating that employees' suggestions are actively used in production processes. As a result, the ratio of implemented and proposed ideas increased, indicating a more efficient use of proposals at the enterprise.

For a more objective assessment of the state of rationalisation and identification of ways to improve it, surveys were conducted among the participants of the rationalisation movement of all categories of employees. At the same time, special attention was paid to the following factors of rationalisation activity: *Motives of participation*, i.e. the reasons that induce workers to take part in the rationalisation movement. The important motives identified in the surveys were the desire to improve working conditions and to obtain rewards both for themselves and their colleagues; *Driving forces* determining the activity of employees in proposing innovative ideas. Among them, initiative, innovativeness and management requirements were found; *Systemic factors* affecting the effectiveness of innovation activity. These include production and management culture, production climate, and support or obstacles from management.

By analysing these factors, it is possible to identify the real problems and challenges faced by those involved in the rationalisation movement and to identify areas for further improvement of the rationalisation system and stimulation of innovation activity in the company. The results of the surveys provide valuable data that can be used by management to create a more favourable and supportive environment for creativity and improvement in the company. It also allows for better interaction between management and employees, contributing to a more effective realisation of ideas and the achievement of the overall goals of the enterprise.

Conclusion. The modern market economy requires constant adaptation and change from enterprises in order to maintain their competitiveness. Effective transformation in both technological

and organisational aspects become a prerequisite for successful functioning of organisations. In the context of economic system transformation and institutional reforms, organisational innovations play a special role. These innovations represent the basis for the creation and implementation of new approaches in the management of enterprises that allow them to adapt to the constantly changing market conditions. Thus, the analysed problems and research methods can become the basis for further research and practical actions in the field of enterprise management taking into account the challenges and prospects of modern economy.

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MARKETING TADQIQOTLARI TIZIMINING METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada marketing tadqiqotlarini o'tkazishning tizimli tahlil, kompleks yondoshuv, chiziqli dasturlash, iqtisodiy va statistik usullar, ekspert baholash, anketa-so'rovnomaga kabi usullarining nazariy jihatlarini ochib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: marketing, bozor, iste'molchi, baho, dala tadqiqotlari, kabinet tadqiqotlari.

Аннотация. В данной статье раскрываются теоретические аспекты таких методов маркетинговых исследований, как системный анализ, комплексный подход, линейное программирование, экономико-статистические методы, экспертная оценка, анкетирование.

Ключевые слова: маркетинг, рынок, потребитель, оценка, полевое исследование, кабинетное исследование.

Abstract. This article reveals the theoretical aspects of such marketing research methods as system analysis, an integrated approach, linear programming, economic and statistical methods, peer review and questionnaire.

Key words: marketing, market, consumer, evaluation, field research, desk research.

Marketing tadqiqotlari turli noaniqliklarni kamaytirish va marketing qarorlarini qabul qilish maqsadida ma'lumotlarni yig'ish, qayta ishlash va tahlil qilish o'z ichiga oladi. Tadqiqotlarda asosan bozor, raqobatchilar, baho hamda korxonaning ichki salohiyati o'rganiladi. Ularni asosi bo'lib, ilmiy va analitik-prognozlashtirish usullari hisobalanadi. Marketing tadqiqotlarini axborot ta'minoti kabinet va tashqi tadqiqotlari, hamda turli xil boshqa axborot manbalari hisobiga shakllantiriladi.

Marketingning metodologik asoslari o'z tarkibiga umumilmiy usullar (tizimli tahlil, kompleks tahlil, dasturiy-maqсадli rejalashtirish), va analitik-prognozlashtirish usullari (chiziqli dasturlash, aloqa nazariyasi, tarmoqlararo rejalashtirish, iqtisodiy-statistik usullari, iqtisodiy-matematik modellashtirish, ekspert usuli) ni oladi[1].

**ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ФАНЛАР АКАДЕМИЯСИ
МИНТАҚАВИЙ БЎЛИМИ
ХОРАЗМ МАЪМУН АКАДЕМИЯСИ**

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